

Deliverable 5.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan – Initial Version

White Research
November 2022

R **BIN**

**DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH**

Funded by
the European Union

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ABBREVIATIONS

DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
CCRI-CSO	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office
D&C	Dissemination and Communication Strategy
SMA	Social Media Accounts

Executive summary

This report constitutes the initial version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) of the Horizon Europe ROBIN project (GA 101060504). The DCP presents the overall strategy that guides the consortium's communication and dissemination activities during the project's implementation. Its purpose is to set a plan for the ROBIN project communication strategy and to maximise the impact throughout its lifecycle.

The report outlines the dissemination and communication strategy of the project, describes the management of the dissemination activities and sets up a detailed monitoring process to ensure its successful implementation. The plan aims to engage a wide range of relevant groups and maximise the project's impact by spreading its outcomes and messages to all the targeted stakeholders and to the general public.

The main sections of the deliverable are presented below:

- Chapter 1: An introduction to the DCP and its goals.
- Chapter 2: A brief description of the ROBIN project.
- Chapter 3: The overview of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy and its objectives.
- Chapter 4: The targeted audience and the respective key messages for the identified stakeholders.
- Chapter 5: The tools and channels used to disseminate and communicate the project's activities and results to the identified targeted stakeholders.
- Chapter 6: This section describes the roles and responsibilities of the dissemination manager and the consortium partners for the successful deployment of the D&C strategy.
- Chapter 7: The importance of establishing synergies with other relevant projects and networks throughout the duration of the project is elaborated on in this chapter.
- Chapter 8: The progress on setting up and operating ROBIN's Advisory Board.
- Chapter 9: This section outlines the Key Performance Indicators that will be used for the evaluation of the dissemination efforts and will permit us to adopt the best practices to increase project's impact. In addition, the reporting process regarding the dissemination activities is also described.
- Chapter 10: The timeline of the four different stages for the implementation of the project's dissemination activities is briefly described in this section.

The Annexes include:

- ➔ The dissemination and communication reporting template: This is the template that all partners need to update on a monthly basis with information about all the dissemination and communication activities.
- ➔ The collaboration agreement signed with BIOMODEL4REGIONS Horizon Europe project.

1. Introduction

It is fundamental to disseminate and effectively communicate the project's vision and results to ensure the successful implementation of ROBIN project. In this context, this deliverable includes the Dissemination and Communication Plan of the project and describes the operational framework for its deployment.

The main objective of ROBIN's Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy is to define the actions carried out and the tools to be used for the promotion of the project's results. On top of that, the strategy aims to provide a specific plan to raise awareness around the project and support ROBIN's implementation. Thus, besides supporting the exploitation of ROBIN outcomes, the DCP ensures the sustainability of the assets developed during the project's lifecycle.

In particular, the DCP offers the answers to some fundamental questions about the communication and dissemination activities of the project:

Table 1. Summary of D&C's key questions

Key questions	ROBIN's DCP
What?	Key messages
To Whom?	Target audiences
Who?	Roles & Responsibilities
How?	Communication tools and channels, guidelines, and templates
When?	Timeline

The dissemination and communication activities will be carried out throughout the duration of the project under the dedicated work package (WP5 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication). Through these activities, the project aspires to engage a large number of stakeholders who could further spread ROBIN's vision and results to wider audiences through their networks, influence, and impact. In addition, the interaction with relevant stakeholders will enable us to receive constant feedback on the project's outcomes.

The DCP, the guidelines, and templates, as well as the Annexes produced in this report, are subject to updates in line with the project's progress. The experience and lessons learned throughout the implementation of the project will permit us to update and modify the strategy - when needed - to be tailored to the needs of our vision. The final version of the D&C strategy is already foreseen by M36 and ensures the continuation of the dissemination of the results even after the completion of ROBIN.

2. About ROBIN project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfill this role with support to co-shape their governance structures to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. The ROBIN project demonstrates the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia, and Greece. ROBIN's team will set up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). The multidisciplinary consortium of ROBIN will provide the regions with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process, ROBIN coordinates its actions with the CCRI-CSO.

The ambition of the EU-funded, ROBIN project is to accelerate the deployment of circular bioeconomy at the regional level in 5 European pilot regions. The project's goal is to support the adaptation of governance models through multi-stakeholder engagement and coordination and promote social innovation.

Thus, the overall objectives of the ROBIN project are:

- ✓ Deeper understanding of existing bioeconomy governance practices and models in Europe
- ✓ Enhanced understanding of the bioeconomy's benefits amongst all stakeholders (including primary biomass producers as well as consumers)
- ✓ Improved regional governance models with increased stakeholder engagement accelerating the circular bioeconomy transition of European regions
- ✓ Better informed bioeconomy strategies creating conducive conditions for investments in sustainable business opportunities offered by local bio-based economies
- ✓ Improved environmental footprint of bio-based products and services
- ✓ Increased cross-regional coordination under the CCRI reinforcing the EU science-policy interface for addressing Sustainable Development Goals

Within the next years, the multidisciplinary consortium of the ROBIN project will organise several events and workshops to inform the audience about important findings and updates on the progress of the project.

Lastly, the dimension of sustainability is pivotal to the goals of the project. As such, the dissemination and communication efforts are vital for the maximisation of its impact and value extraction. Creating multiple channels for taking advantage of the project assets is a key priority for ROBIN and it becomes apparent that dissemination and communication activities are significant, as they leverage the sustainability of the project's positive impacts.

3. Dissemination and communication strategy

3.1. Overview

The DCP of ROBIN describes the overall D&C strategy of the project concerning the dissemination and communication of the outcomes. The strategy is carefully designed and tailored to the approach of the project aiming to maximise its impact, transfer knowledge and the results to the targeted stakeholders, as well as to communicate its concept to wider audiences. The D&C strategy is translated into a robust plan by considering multiple key elements as illustrated in the figure below and described in the next chapters.

Figure 1. Overview of ROBIN's D&C strategy

This section presents the overview of the D&C strategy and outlines the structure of the DCP. First of all, the first sub-section of this chapter presents the objectives of the DCP which will be used to monitor the successful implementation of the strategy. The next chapter defines the target audience i.e., to whom we will disseminate the project's results. On top of that, the next sub-section presents the key messages for each one of the targeted stakeholders, as well as the core visions and assets. A dedicated section of the strategy focuses on the means, channels, and tools that will be used to reach the identified stakeholders. Additionally, the allocation of roles and responsibilities for the dissemination strategy are clearly elaborated to ensure the smooth and effective implementation of the DCP.

Throughout the duration of the project, special attention will be given to cooperation with other relevant projects at national and European levels. Although there is a dedicated task (T5.3) for establishing synergies with other relevant projects and networks, the document presents a short introduction regarding the initial plan. Lastly, the next chapters unveil a robust framework for the assessment of the strategy along with a timeline for the dissemination and communication steps.

Aiming to ensure the successful dissemination and communication of results, the DCP constitutes a guiding document that presents the tools and actions which will navigate the consortium partners to successfully engage the targeted stakeholders. Of course, the DCP is dynamic and flexible, meaning that it can be reviewed and updated - if this is necessary - during the lifecycle of the project.

3.2. Objectives of the DCP

The D&C strategy of ROBIN sets a list of practical and realistic objectives that will ensure the effective monitoring and consequently the successful implementation of the dissemination and communication activities of the project. These objectives answer the question of WHY the DCP is needed. The dissemination and communication objectives of ROBIN are briefly presented below:

- Present the project's aim, vision, activities, and events to a wider audience;
- Promote awareness raising among stakeholder groups;
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities;
- Engage stakeholders through a series of relevant activities, events, and conferences;
- Ensure that the key messages are communicated to its target audiences;
- Ensure the exploitation of the project's outcomes;
- Plan, organise, monitor, and fine-tune the project's dissemination activities and events;
- Establish and sustain synergies with other relevant national and European projects and networks;
- Disseminate the project's lessons learned and outcomes in an open and transparent way.

4. Target audience and key messages

4.1. Target audience

One of the most critical steps for the successful development of the D&C strategy is to answer the question “to Whom?”. Who are the main stakeholders that the project aims to engage and transfer its messages and results to? This section presents the main target audiences that ROBIN expects to reach during its lifecycle. The figure below briefly presents the target audiences:

Figure 2. ROBIN target audiences

ROBIN aims to engage a wide variety of stakeholders with different backgrounds and experiences. In particular:

1. Policy actors (Directorate Generals of the European Commission, EU policymakers, National governments, Local governments, Regional authorities, Policy advisors)
2. Civil society (consumers, clusters & action groups)
3. Researchers & academia
4. Horizon projects, CCRI & other EU initiatives
5. Regional bioeconomy actors (e.g., primary biomass producers)
6. Bio-based SMEs & Industries (e.g., biobased industrial companies)
7. Innovation & policy advisors
8. Financial Institutions
9. Bioeconomy Experts
10. General public
11. International Organisations

During the project’s lifespan, it remains important to classify them to better prioritise and fine-tune our engagement efforts. To this aim, the Stakeholders Classification Model¹ is used in order to classify each targeted stakeholder group based on the following parameters:

- The extent of a stakeholder’s power/authority;
- The stakeholder’s interest regarding the outcomes of the project;
- The extent of the stakeholder’s active involvement in the project;
- The level of stakeholder’s influence over the project planning and/or outcomes.

Figure 3. Stakeholder mapping and types of stakeholder engagement

The D&C strategy aims to reach the above-mentioned identified audiences which were further categorised into the broader ROBIN stakeholder groups. A more detailed elaboration on the targeted stakeholders and specific examples are offered in the following Table:

Table 2. ROBIN target audience categories

Target Group	Short description	Sub-categories
Policy actors	Decision-makers at European, national, and regional levels that are expected to play a key role in policy design.	Directorate Generals of the European Commission EU policymakers National governments Local governments Regional authorities Policy advisors
Bioeconomy industry & actors	All actors that are active in the field of bioeconomy and regional development.	Biobased SMEs Bioeconomy experts Biobased industrial companies

¹ Emerson Wagner Mainardes, Helena Alves, Mário Raposo, (2012). “A model for stakeholder classification and stakeholder relationships”, Management Decision, Vol. 50 Issue: 10, pp. 1861-1879.

		Innovation Advisors Investors Regional bioeconomy actors Primary biomass producers
Scientific community	Network of interacting scientists who conduct research in the fields of bioeconomy, regional development, and biobased products	Research Centres Research groups Individual researchers Universities
Civil Society	Individuals who are interested in enhancing their knowledge of bioeconomy, biobased products	General public Consumers Clusters Action Groups
Relevant EU projects, CCRI & other EU initiatives	Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects as well as other European and national projects and initiatives	CCRI H2020 projects Horizon Europe projects Other EU-funded projects (e.g., Interreg, Erasmus+)
Organisations & Institutions	Organisations (governmental and non-governmental) and Institutions that are active in the bioeconomy field	International Organisations NGOs Financial Institutions Governmental Institutions

4.2. Key messages and vision

4.2.1. Key messages

Another important step for establishing a successful D&C strategy is to determine WHAT will be communicated to the stakeholders. In the previous section, the first identification of the most critical stakeholder groups to be reached in the framework of the project took place. These groups consist of stakeholders with different backgrounds and needs, therefore different messages should be communicated to them. These messages will be updated over the course of the project based on the experience acquired during the implementation of the activities. Furthermore, the project aims to exploit the extended network of consortium partners in order to reach a wide pool of individuals. Table 3 lists the targeted stakeholder groups along with their needs and tailored messages. However, the final key messages will be defined throughout the project's lifecycle based on the actual ROBIN data and outcomes.

Table 3. ROBIN target audience, needs and messages

Target Group	Needs	Messages
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Policy actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Understand the current landscape of regional bioeconomy governance models – Explore new ways of establishing regional governance models with a focus on bioeconomy – Better informed and effective policies for developing regional governance models with a focus on bioeconomy – Explore new ways of engaging stakeholders from different backgrounds – Develop new regional strategies – Integrate social innovation into the policy development process – More examples of applied best practices and how to replicate them – Enhance the knowledge of how to coordinate CCRI actions with EU-funded projects – Achieve progress toward meeting regional, national, and EU policy targets – Introduce a more socio-economic and environmental approach to the development of regional governance models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Increased policy recommendations on how to create regional bioeconomy models ✓ Enhanced engagement of stakeholders in bioeconomy models ✓ Improved, more inclusive, and better-informed governance models based on stakeholder engagement ✓ Further insights on local potentialities along with the means to tap into them for stimulating bio-based and social innovation ✓ Increased support to raise awareness amongst regional bioeconomy stakeholders and engage them in building and improving governance models
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Bioeconomy industry & actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increase the market penetration of biobased innovations – Develop bio-based value chains that deliver sustainable products/ services – Capitalise on emerging investment opportunities in bio-based sectors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Increased networking and stakeholder engagement opportunities to build connections required to accelerate bio-based innovation ✓ Enhanced integration of bio-based value chain development into broader policies and regional development plans ✓ Increased awareness of bioeconomy and its benefits ✓ Increased demand for bio-based products/services

<p>Scientific community</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Advance research in focal scientific fields related to bioeconomy – Keep in line with industry and policy developments in the bioeconomy field – Follow recent developments and research trends – Identify research gaps for further research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Aggregation and classification of existing scientific knowledge of types of bioeconomy governance models ✓ New knowledge and empirical open data on the application of novel inclusive governance models
<p>Society</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increased socioeconomic and environmental benefits from established policies – Plethora of more sustainable, healthier, and affordable products and services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ A more meaningful engagement in regional bioeconomy governance and policy making ✓ Increased understanding of the bioeconomy and how to make better-informed and more sustainable choices.
<p>Relevant EU projects, CCRI & other EU initiatives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Exchange knowledge with other experts in the field – Share their results and promote their concept to other initiatives and the general public – Establish synergies and expand their network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Deliverables with the project results to enhance further research in the field ✓ A network of synergies that facilitates collaboration and knowledge transfer between relevant initiatives ✓ Increased support in the dissemination of the project's results
<p>Organisations & Institutions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Stay updated regarding the latest developments in the bioeconomy and policy development field – Engage and inform more citizens about social innovative governance structures on bioeconomy – Stay informed about the progress regarding the establishment of regional bioeconomy models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Ways to integrate best practices derived from the project into the development of regional bioeconomy models

The abovementioned messages are subject to change to reflect the actual needs of stakeholders, as identified during the first engagement activities of the project. The final key messages will be updated and refined throughout the project based on the experience acquired during its implementation.

5. Communication and dissemination tools and channels

ROBIN's DCP will deploy multiple tools and channels in order to ensure that activities and produced outcomes will reach a wide variety of stakeholders and will contribute to the uptake of circular bioeconomies in regional level. An overview of the different tools, channels, and planned dissemination activities is presented in Figure 4, showcasing HOW the D&C strategy will be implemented.

Figure 4. ROBIN's communication activities

ROBIN'S promotional material and graphical identity include:

- Project logo
- Project's visual and graphical identity
- Leaflet
- Poster
- Templates (e.g., for publications and presentations)
- Letterhead
- Ad-hoc promotional material (tailored to the project's activities and needs – if needed)

ROBIN'S online presence includes:

- Website
- Bi-annual newsletters
- Facebook page
- Twitter account
- LinkedIn profile
- YouTube channel
- Promotional video

ROBIN'S events include:

- Engagement events
- Participation in external events and conferences as ROBIN representatives
- Final dissemination event
- Co- organisation and participation in events with projects that we have established synergies (e.g., webinars, workshops, joint Final Conference)

ROBIN'S publications include:

- Project's deliverables
- Scientific publications
- Other publications in different media (e.g., articles, press releases, etc.)

The following sub-chapters offer a detailed description of the abovementioned tools and channels.

5.1. Promotional material

The promotional material of ROBIN was prepared during the early stages of the project. WR was responsible for the graphic design and the content, while the consortium partners offered feedback throughout the development process. The material will be freely available to the public through the project's website (online for download) and the partners will print and distributed it when needed. The material will be used during physical activities (including external and project events) to attract and engage relevant stakeholders and give more information on the project's mission and objectives.

All the promotional material is designed based on the project's unique identity which is presented in the following paragraph.

5.1.1. Project logo

The early design of the graphical identity of ROBIN in terms of the project's logo and templates will ensure consistency throughout the project. Therefore, the project's logo and visual identity have already been developed (M1) to satisfy the visual requirements of the project. The logo will make the project recognisable and will form the basis for the design of all the promotional material, which will be used for the different promotional and communication materials (e.g., leaflets, posters, newsletters, deliverables, social media, web-portal, publications, publicity for internal and external events, etc.).

During the kick-off meeting of the project, various logo options were presented to the partners to state their preferences and select their favorite design. WR presented the different options to partners, which in turn voted online on their preference. Taking into consideration partners' preferences, WR opted for the more popular logo. The final logo is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. ROBIN project logo

The ROBIN logo should be visible to all the communication material produced in the framework of the project (presentation, deliverables, etc.). Similarly, the EU funding should be properly acknowledged, and the EU emblem should also be properly depicted in all communication material.

Figure 6. The emblem of the European Union

The EU flag will be always accompanied by the following statement: *“Funded by the European Union”*

5.1.2. Leaflet and poster

A trifold leaflet and a poster were prepared to be distributed by the partners in physical events and activities but also to be uploaded on the project’s website. Both the poster and leaflet will be used to attract stakeholders’ attention and provide brief information about the ROBIN project.

The leaflet presents the project’s aim to empower Europe’s regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts. The poster focuses more on attracting the stakeholders’ attention with graphical elements and offers some basic information on the project and the key stakeholder groups.

Both items provide information about the partners involved, together with contact, website and SMAs details as well as acknowledge the funding the project receives through the Horizon Europe program.

The draft versions of the project leaflet and poster are illustrated in Figure 7 and Figure 8, respectively. The final versions of both may undergo modifications based on the comments collected from the project coordinator and the partners. The final version will be presented in the Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results – Interim Version.

OUR TEAM

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The project

ROBIN aims to empower Europe's regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.

IT WILL SUPPORT 5 REGIONAL AUTHORITIES ACROSS EUROPE TO:

- adapt their governance models to support the scaling up of the bio-based value chains of their ecosystem
- exploit existing knowledge from earlier work and knowhow in bioeconomy policy and social innovation
- network and source knowledge from peers and consort with the European Commission's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO).

PROJECT ID

PROJECT NAME: ROBIN
"Deploying circular bioeconomies at regional level with a territorial approach"
GRANT AGREEMENT: 101060504
PROGRAMME: Horizon Europe
TYPE OF ACTION: HORIZON-CSA
START DATE: 1 September 2022
DURATION: 36 months
EU CONTRIBUTION: 2,499,951.00€
COORDINATOR: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC

ROBIN

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

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The Challenge

Europe's regional authorities can play a crucial role in the socioeconomic development of their local ecosystems; yet, most of European regions are still exploring their position concerning bioeconomy. Bioeconomy can be a key pillar when it comes to a more circular and sustainable ways of development and Europe's regional governments should adapt their governance models and structures to enable practical applications of bioeconomy-related knowledge and advances. The newest policy mandates in the field of circularity increase the complexity of needed and expects actions for an integrated transition; however recently, high-quality knowledge has been developed to guide the bioeconomy transition.

Territorial approach

A territorial approach is followed in the deployment of circular bio-economies at regional level, which enables to:

- Focus on functional distribution of space based on degree of rurality / urbanisation (rural – semi rural – peri-urban – urban)
- Examine the natural, geographical, economic, social, political features of the region
- Examine the central control and the hierarchical organisation of networks within space
- Examine how the regional ecosystem is affected by spatial planning policies (regional development plans, urban development plans, etc.)

OUR OBJECTIVES

- Deeper understanding of existing bioeconomy governance practices and models in Europe
- Enhanced understanding of the bioeconomy's benefits amongst all stakeholders (including primary biomass producers as well as consumers)
- Improved regional governance models with increased stakeholder engagement accelerating the circular bioeconomy transition of European regions
- Better informed bioeconomy strategies creating conducive conditions for investments in sustainable business opportunities offered by local bio-based economies
- Improved environmental footprint of bio-based products and services
- Increased cross-regional coordination under the CCRI reinforcing the EU science-policy interface for addressing Sustainable Development Goals

5 steps to innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in the ROBIN Regions

STEP 1 Set the scene on regional bioeconomy governance models
ROBIN explores the existing governance models in Europe, develops a typology of these models and identifies good governance practices. It deepens the knowledge around the barriers, challenges and opportunities for the uptake of circular bioeconomy governance models through consultation with and active engagement of regional quadruple helix stakeholder representatives included in the Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARCs) of the project.

STEP 2 Co-create regional governance models and structures
Through a bottom-up approach, ROBIN engages the MARCs to co create governance models that overcome barriers and seize opportunities for circular bioeconomy. Moreover, it develops a practical Toolbox that contains actionable knowledge, a portfolio of coordination and support actions and user-friendly tools.

STEP 3 Set up and validate the ROBIN Toolbox
ROBIN deploys the ROBIN Toolbox within diverse territorial contexts across 5 European regions aiming at supporting the development and operation of governance models towards circular bioeconomy transition. The diversity of pilot regions in terms of socioeconomic, institutional and ecological features enable the replication of results.

STEP 4 Monitor & Evaluate results – Share of best practices
ROBIN exchanges best practices among regions, to promote the development of cross-regional partnerships on regional bioeconomy, transfer knowledge and experience, build partnerships and enhance openness, transparency and engagement. Also, it develops an integrated replication guideline with the generated knowledge and tools which are validated through a robust monitoring and evaluation framework.

STEP 5 Communicate & Deploy synergies
ROBIN supports the dissemination and communication of its results through a tailored strategy involving the set-up of ROBIN Advisory Board, while also creating synergies with key European and national networks, as well as the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI-CSO), Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO).

Figure 7. The front and back side of the draft version of ROBIN leaflet

Figure 8. The draft version of ROBIN poster

The ROBIN website visitors will be able to easily download the leaflet and the poster.

5.1.3. Publication templates

Besides the poster and the leaflet, templates have also been prepared in line with the graphical identity of the project to be used during dissemination activities. The developed templates include:

- The ROBIN .ppt presentation template (to be used by the consortium partners during events and meetings)
- Reports template (to be used for the project’s deliverables and other publications)
- Letterheads (to be used for an official invitation to events)

The presentation and reports template are presented in Figure 9 and Figure 10, respectively.

Figure 9. ROBIN .ppt presentation template

Figure 10. ROBIN reports template

All partners should use the official project’s templates when preparing presentations or reports in the framework of the project.

5.1.4. Promotional video

The promotional video of the project will be produced in M12. The video will present in very simple terms a short introduction to the project, its objectives, and actions and will give an overview of its outcomes. The video will be uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel, the project’s website, and the other SMAs.

5.1.5. Other promotional material

ROBIN aspires to produce additional promotional material to attract the attention of the targeted groups. To this aim, material such as ad-hoc press releases, articles, and publications will be developed. More specifically, press releases will be published when major achievements and milestones are reached to inform of the progress of the project. Besides presenting key outcomes, general press releases may also be produced to promote project events and attract media attention.

5.2 Digital tools

Gradually, more people select to get informed through digital communication channels. To better communicate its messages, ROBIN will focus on building a strong online presence on multiple digital platforms aiming to reach as many diverse stakeholders as possible. In particular, ROBIN will create:

- (i) a website;
- (ii) bi-annual newsletters;
- (iii) various SMAs

5.2.1. ROBIN website

ROBIN website will be launched on M4 (December 2022) and will constitute the key digital dissemination platform of the project, presenting its progress to wider audiences. The website will be accessible to the general public and therefore its structure and content are designed in a user-friendly way to keep the stakeholders engaged.

Key information about the concept and the approach of ROBIN is presented, along with the team members and the members of the Advisory Board. All project outcomes such as public reports, dissemination material, and newsletters will be free to download. Since the territorial approach and Multi-Actor Regional Constellations are a key asset of the project, the website will include a dedicated section for the pilot regions. Also, a direct link to the ROBIN’s Toolbox will be included in the project’s website. The project’s Privacy policy will be also available on the website.

Although WR, as the dissemination manager, will be the main responsible for the website management and content, all partners will contribute to the content development with news and other dissemination material. The website will remain active throughout the duration of the project and will include regular updates on the progress of the project, internal and external events, relevant projects and initiatives, reports and project results, as well as other news from the bioeconomy field.

At the current stage, a draft structure of the expected website has been formulated. Later, the final version will be presented in the updated version of the interim version of the DCP (M18). An indicative structure of the website is presented in Figure 11. The structure constitutes a baseline for the website and will be updated, when necessary, to be in line with the project’s requirements and progress. The URL for the website is expected to be <https://robin-project.eu/> and the contact email for the project will be in line with it (info@robin-project.eu). For the monitoring of the website’s traffic, the Google

Analytics service will be used. This tool provides useful statistics that will help to optimise the website and dissemination strategy.

Figure 11. Indicative structure of the website

5.2.2. Newsletter

Bi-annual newsletters will be produced in the framework of the project and will be distributed to the project’s community. The newsletter will engage the audience who is not familiar with social media and will keep stakeholders constantly updated about the project. The newsletter among others will include updates on the progress of the project, will introduce the project’s concept, and will disseminate upcoming project events and activities.

WR will be responsible for releasing the newsletter, but all partners will be responsible for providing input and content for each issue as requested by the dissemination manager.

Mailchimp will be employed for the development and distribution of the newsletter. Also, each partner will have the option to send the newsletter in their own organisations mailing list. Although the content of each issue will be agreed upon by the partners, in general, will indicatively include the following sections:

- An introductory section briefly describing the ROBIN project
- Progress updates
- A project’s news section including articles which will describe the main activities that were carried out during the last six months
- A section dedicated to future developments (e.g., upcoming events, publications, etc.)
- A section listing other relevant major events
- Other types of relevant articles
- News from bioeconomy / regional development sector

For the subscription to the newsletter all GDPR provisions will be followed. The subscribers will be asked to agree with the Privacy Policy of the project, and they will have an option to unsubscribe from the newsletter at any time.

The Newsletter will be sent to all the subscribers and recipients upon its release and each issue will be also uploaded on the project's website.

5.2.3. Social Media Accounts (SMAs)

Besides the ROBIN website, various SMAs were already established to promote the project and its vision. Nowadays, SMAs offer the ability to build digital communities and attract followers that could transfer and multiply the project's vision even after the completion of the project. Therefore, a large pool of interested stakeholders will be actively engaged on a regular basis through ROBIN's SMAs. In particular, the Facebook page, Twitter account, LinkedIn profile, and YouTube channel have been established by M2 of the project. Four different social media platforms have been selected to ensure the maximum dissemination of the results in media addressing different types of stakeholders.

The target audiences addressed by each social media channel and the specific objectives are presented in Table 4:

Table 4. The target audiences addressed by each social media channel

Social Network	ROBIN Target Audience	Objectives
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Biobased SMEs – Biobased industrial companies – Primary biomass producers – Investors – Regional bioeconomy actors – General public – Consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Build a network of followers ✓ Update them on the project's progress and project events ✓ Publish relevant posts
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Directorate Generals of the European Commission – EU policymakers – National governments – Local governments – Regional authorities – Policy advisors – Individual researchers – Bioeconomy Clusters - Action Groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Communicate key messages and the project's outcomes ✓ Announce project and upcoming events ✓ Retweet relevant content from other Horizon Europe/ H2020 projects

LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – EU policymakers – Policy advisors – Bioeconomy experts – Innovation Advisors – Research Centers – Research groups – Individual researchers – Universities – International Organisations – NGOs – Financial Institutions – Governmental Institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Present the project and boost professional and expert discussions
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – EU policymakers – Bioeconomy experts – Innovation Advisors – Investors – Regional bioeconomy actors – Primary biomass producers – Research Centers – Research groups – Individual researchers – General public – Consumers – Clusters – Action Groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Upload promotional video ✓ Contribute to increasing the visibility of the project

WR is responsible for the management of ROBIN's SMAs, while all partners are expected to contribute by:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile);
- Promoting the accounts in their networks;
- Suggesting relevant profiles that ROBIN should connect with;
- Sharing interesting articles and news with WR, to be promoted through the project's SMA;
- Promoting ROBIN posts and news through the SMAs of their own organisations.

5.2.3.1. Facebook

ROBIN's Facebook page was established in M2. The Facebook page is used to promote the project's results and progress and share news about interesting topics from the sector. Different types of posts will be made including text and videos. In addition, invitations will be sent to followers for the events organised in the framework of the project. Specifically, ROBIN's Facebook account will serve as a:

- News and discussion hub where information or news related to the project and topics of bioeconomy, certification, and circular economy will be shared;
- Platform to deliver updates about developments and results of the project (e.g., published reports, scientific publications, key events, activities, important achievements);
- Link to other similar groups and pages associated with relevant topics.

Figure 12. Screenshot of ROBIN's Facebook page

To monitor the performance of the ROBIN page, Facebook Analytics will be used.

5.2.3.2. Twitter

Similarly, the ROBIN Twitter account was launched in M2. Twitter is an important dissemination tool for ROBIN as it will enable the ROBIN team to stay updated on the news from the sector and the outcomes of relevant projects. The Twitter platform will contribute to the establishment of new synergies with similar initiatives and steer attention toward our concept. The use of hashtags allows the project's messages to reach wider audiences and the short and precise posts' text can actively engage a large pool of stakeholders. In addition, the account is excellent for the effective dissemination of events.

In this context, the Twitter account will act as a:

- General dissemination platform that will include the key messages of the project will direct users to other project-related platforms/tools (e.g., ROBIN's website, newsletter promotional video) and will communicate information on the project's development (upcoming events, participation in external events, project results, etc.);
- Newsfeed platform collecting and updating news from other relevant projects and organisations;
- Engage and create a community of followers interested in the topic and sector.

The project partners are expected to contribute to the Twitter account on a regular basis by retweeting its content via their personal accounts and suggesting relevant content. Twitter analytics will be used to monitor the account's performance. A snapshot of the account is provided in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Screenshot of ROBIN's Twitter account

5.2.3.3. LinkedIn

The LinkedIn platform was selected to promote the project to a more professional audience. The profile of the project was set in M2 in order to present the project and offer updates on its progress. ROBIN partners are expected to support the project's LinkedIn profile and invite followers.

The metrics and insights provided by LinkedIn will be utilised to assess the project's performance.

Figure 14. Screenshot of ROBIN's LinkedIn account

5.2.3.4. YouTube

YouTube has been selected as the final digital channel for communicating the project's identity and goals. Therefore, a YouTube profile for ROBIN is created to aggregate all the videos produced in the frame of the project in a single and easily accessible location, aiming to increase its visibility and bring it closer to the audience. The YouTube profile will create a visual community and leverage the features of videos to effectively promote the project's activities in an appealing and effective way.

The main promotional video for ROBIN will be produced in M12 to raise awareness and create ripple effects that contribute to the project's visibility. A snapshot of the account is provided in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Screenshot of ROBIN's YouTube account

5.3. Events

ROBIN will participate in several events to promote its outcomes and expand its influence on how to deploy regional governance models with a focus on bioeconomy.

5.3.1. Project events

The events organised in the framework of ROBIN aim to raise awareness around the concept of the project, promote the project's results and facilitate the engagement of key stakeholders which will support the project's activities and provide feedback on the produced outcomes. Several events, such as stakeholder engagement events, mutual learning workshops, and a final dissemination event will promote the exploitation of ROBIN's results.

A series of events will be organised to:

- (i) align ROBIN'S support actions to regional needs (co-creation workshops);
- (ii) design tailored action plans (action plan workshop);
- (iii) catalyse connections and enhance understanding of bioeconomy amongst regional stakeholders (stakeholder engagement events);
- (iv) exchange knowledge across regions (mutual learning workshops);
- (v) build capacity amongst stakeholders around Europe (train-the-trainers event); and
- (vi) disseminate final results (final event in M36).

Explicitly, the following types of events are scheduled as part of the project's plan:

Table 5. ROBIN's internal events

Event	WP, Task, responsible partner	Short description	Date (estimation)
5 regional co-creation events (one in each region) comprised of 2 sessions	WP2, T2.1, CTA, support: all	<p>Session 1: Validation and prioritisation of key barriers, potentialities, and opportunities to be pursued;</p> <p>Session 2: Definition of improvement areas for current governance model(s) & co-creation of new one(s) (including novel business models and social measures)</p>	M1-M15
Action Plan Workshop	WP2, T2.2, CTA, support: all	A workshop where the regional partners will shape Action Plans detailing the specific support actions that will be offered in their region. The concrete output of this task is an Action Plan for each ROBIN region (D2.2)	M10-M16
Regional partners will run 2 stakeholder engagement events	WP3, T3.2, BPRO, support: all	Events to engage stakeholders in the frame of the support actions where feedback will be collected from major testing	M18-M30
Digital validation workshop	WP3, T3.3, S2I, support: all	Validation workshop of the Toolbox with the Advisory Board	M16-M32
2 mutual learning workshops and missions (DE and SK)	WP4, T4.2, CTA, support: all	In collaboration with the respective regional partners to exchange information	M18-M34
Train-the-Trainer event	WP4, T4.2, CTA, support: all	An event that will open the way for building the capacity	M18-M34
Final dissemination event	WP5, T5.1, WR, support: all	Final event and dissemination of ROBIN's results	M36
<i>In total at least 22 workshops and events will be organised within WP1 – WP5</i>			

5.3.2. External events and conferences

Besides organising events in the framework of the project, the consortium partners will also attend external events and conferences with the aim to reach a wide audience relevant to ROBIN's objectives. During these events the partners will:

- Present the project (concept, approach, etc.);
- Promote the project's results;
- Promote ROBIN's actions and events;
- Establish synergies and contacts with relevant projects and initiatives;
- Engage relevant stakeholders in the project's activities;
- Promote the project's dissemination channels (website, SMAs, etc.).

The partners participating in external events should always follow the visual identity of the project and use the official promotional material (leaflet, poster, .ppt template, etc.). In case of participation in an external event with the aim to present ROBIN, partners should send the final presentation to WR **at least 5 working days prior to the event**. In addition, the partners should always inform WR in advance regarding their participation in an external event to be appropriately disseminated through the project's dissemination accounts. Finally, after actual participation, partners should fill in the reporting template (Annex I) and send it back to WR.

An indicative list of identified conferences and events is provided below:

Table 6. ROBIN's external events and conferences

Conferences & Events	Short description	Link
European Bioeconomy Network Events	The European Bioeconomy Network is a proactive alliance of EU-funded projects dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication, and support.	https://eubionet.eu/events/
European Biomass Conference	The EUBCE is the leading platform for the collection, exchange, and dissemination of scientific and industrial know-how in the field of biomass.	https://www.eubce.com/
European Forum for Industrial Biotechnology & Bioeconomy	EFIB is the market-leading annual event in Europe for Industrial Biotechnology and the Bioeconomy.	https://efibforum.com/
European Week of Regions and Cities	Annual event during which cities and regions showcase their capacity to create growth and jobs and prove the importance of local governance in Europe.	https://europa.eu/regions-and-cities/

International Bioeconomy Conference	An inter and transdisciplinary meeting for experts and stakeholders dedicated to systemic approaches of a sustainable bioeconomy, held in Baden-Württemberg.	https://biooekonomie.baden-wuerttemberg.de/Lde/Startseite/Biooekonomiekongress
International Consortium on Applied Bioeconomy Research	Consortium on bioeconomy, agricultural biotechnology, rural development, and bio-based economy research topics.	https://icabr.net/

By the time this DCP was produced, ROBIN partners had already participated in some external events, presented in Table 7.

Table 7. List of external events where ROBIN members participated

Event Title	Date	Brief Description of ROBIN Participation
EuBioNet annual MML workshop “Projects2projects” – outcomes and material	October 2022	Participation at workshop with representatives of cities, regions and other Horizon Europe & Horizon 2020 CCRI-CSO. Brief introduction of ROBIN, networking and information exchange with other projects.
1st CCRI Coordination and Support Workshop: “Getting started”	October 2022	Participation to a joint workshop with representatives of other Horizon Circular Cities projects. Round table for introducing ROBIN and receive information about the progress of other projects.

5.4 Publications

5.4.1. Scientific publications

Scientific publications are important significant channels for presenting ROBIN’s outcomes to academic, research, and industrial target audiences. Thus, creating knowledge impact and enabling other researchers and stakeholders to use the project’s results in their own work contributes to disseminating the project further. **Open access publications in peer-reviewed platforms (at least 3)** will also be employed for disseminating key project results, along with events and other communication activities. Scientific publications will be offered with green or gold open access to Open Research Europe, an open peer review venue, which will enable ROBIN’s team not only to share the project’s results rapidly but also to facilitate open, constructive research discussions to enhance their quality and relevance.

Since ROBIN’s consortium supports open access to scientific publications, all necessary steps will be taken to ensure free access to peer-reviewed articles resulting from the project. Actions in this regard will include the following alternatives as described in the Open Data Strategy of the EC and will follow the FAIR approach. ROBIN’s research outputs will be accessible to the public in a digital and online way, and free of charge. Therefore:

- i. Research deliverables will be published on the project’s web portal;

- ii. Scientific publications will be immediately open and accessible through a trusted repository (e.g., Open Research Europe, European Open Science Cloud) (“green” or “gold” open access).

Green open access: Deposit an electronic copy of the published version or the final manuscript accepted for publication in a scientific publication relating to the project’s foreground in an institutional or subject-based repository at the moment of publication. The beneficiaries will make their best efforts to ensure that this electronic copy becomes freely and electronically available to anyone through this repository within 6 months from the publication date. The exact selection of the repository, the terms under which access will be granted, and all other relevant details will be decided when the publication is available.

Gold open access: Immediately provide the article in open access mode, with the payment of publication costs being shifted away from readers. The costs (Author Processing Charges) will be paid by the partners supporting the research.

The strategy foresees at least 3 scientific publications in the framework of the project. An indicative list of scientific journals can be found below:

Table 8. An indicative list of pre-selected scientific journals for ROBIN's scientific publications

Journal	Impact factor
Bio-Based Materials and Energy under Circular Economy Approaches	3.889
Innovation and Sustainable Development for the Bioeconomy	3.889
Sustainability: Science, Practice, and Policy	2.917
Sustainability	3.251

5.3.3. Non-scientific publications

Throughout the duration of the ROBIN project, all partners will be invited to produce press and media releases, articles in mass media, and presentations on TV or radio, or other media. The aim of all these efforts is to increase the project’s visibility and publicity and the potential to reach out to stakeholders outside of the consortium.

Lastly, all partners are responsible for identifying publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure the promotion of the project’s assets and results. Additionally, this strategy does not foresee a minimum number of non-scientific publications. However, track of published material will be kept through the Dissemination Reporting Template (Annex I) on a monthly basis.

6. Roles and responsibilities

The allocation of responsibilities answers the question of **who** is going to implement the DCP. In order to achieve the defined objectives, the implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy will be a collective effort from all consortium partners. WR as the dissemination and communication manager monitors the implemented activities and the progress towards the realisation of the DCP objectives. Partners' contribution will be a natural by-product of the project's development as most activities, results, milestones, and progress will either involve stakeholder engagement and communication or turn into assets that should be adequately promoted. The partners will contribute to the offline activities by organising events, planning dissemination activities, and participating in external events and conferences to raise awareness. In addition, they are expected to be involved in online dissemination activities by providing content and promoting the digital dissemination tools of the project. More specifically consortium partners should:

Online dissemination activities:

- Provide content for the website, SMAs, and the newsletter (The contribution could be a suggestion for a Facebook or Twitter post, an article regarding the project or a relevant topic of the sector, or an interview). The goals are to ensure a constant flow of content around the project's actions and keep our online presence active and useful for the relevant stakeholders.
- Promote the website, SMAs, and newsletter through their network.
- Inform the dissemination manager about relevant events or news of the sector that could be used for content creation

Physical dissemination activities:

- Organise events and raise awareness around the project
- Disseminate the promotional material of the project (leaflet, poster, etc.)
- All partners through their participation in external events and conferences and through publications for online/offline sources (websites, newspapers, magazines, etc.) should ensure the widest exposure and dissemination of the project.

Activities reporting:

All partners must report the carried-out dissemination and communication activities to the dissemination manager. More information about the process will follow in the respective chapter.

7. Networks and synergies

Collaboration and establishment of synergies for the dissemination of the project's results are pivotal for its successful implementation. To that end, Task 5.3 aims to search for alignment with relevant initiatives and projects working on similar topics. The project has already established synergies with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) and the Horizon Europe project BIOMODEL4REGIONS that under the same topic.

Over the course of the project ROBIN partners will:

1. Cooperate with initiatives and projects working on similar topics
2. Seek and establish synergies with projects that are relevant to the topic

The cooperation may take various forms. Indicatively:

- Mutual dissemination of events in our SMAs and the website
- Mutual reference of projects on respective websites
- Organisation of joint activities (e.g., workshops, dissemination events, etc.)
- Participation in the project's events
- Exchange of news, experiences
- Co-participate in conferences
- Co-write press releases, articles, etc.

Multiple potential joint activities will be also identified throughout the whole duration of the project and will be reported in the respective deliverable.

From the initial stages of the project several potential networks and relevant projects have been identified.

Table 9. An indicative list of ROBIN's dissemination networks

Multiplier for dissemination	Partner(s) that act as contact points
ERRIN Circular Bioeconomy working group	CAG, CTA
BIC bioeconomy platform	BIOPRO, CTA, RCM, CAG
Platform of Bioeconomy ERA NET Actions	RCM
S3P Traceability & Big Data	IFA, CTA, CAG
European Cluster Collaboration Platform	CTA
EITFood	CAG
European Committee of Regions	RCM, CAG, SRA, ZSK
SDSN Black Sea	AUTh
European Alliance for Innovation	PED

European Bioeconomy Alliance	RCM
COOPID Bioeconomy Clusters	MTU
European Bioeconomy Network	QPL, WR
Climate Pact Secretariat	PED

The initial list will be constantly updated during the duration of the project in order to identify new opportunities for collaboration.

Table 10. Indicative list with projects for potential synergies

Acronym	Title	Website
Agro2Circular	New ways to upcycle agri-food packaging	https://agro2circular.eu/
TREASoURcE	Boost innovative circular economy practices to make sustainable products the norm	https://treasource.eu/
SYSCHEMIQ	Systemic solutions for the territorial deployment of the circular economy	Under development
BIOMODEL4REGIONS	Supporting the establishment of the innovative governance models in the bio-based economy	https://www.biomodel4regions.eu/
BIOBOOST	Biomass based energy intermediates boosting biofuel production	https://bioboost.eu/

A template of a collaboration agreement has been prepared to establish cooperation with other projects and initiatives. Both the template and the signed collaboration agreement with BIOMODEL4REGIONS project for joint dissemination and communication activities, can be found in Annex II.

8. Set up and operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board

One of the first tasks of ROBIN was to set up an Advisory Board to act as an external consultation body to the project and share its knowledge and expertise with the partners of the project at key stages of its implementation. In fact, following a tailored set up process (see Figure 16), the ROBIN AB has been started to be composed, ensuring diverse expertise, gender mix and geographic spread among the members.

Figure 16. ROBIN Advisory Board set-up process

The members of the ROBIN Advisory Board:

- act as a consultation body for the ROBIN consortium, providing the consortium with strategic guidance and feedback in key stages of the project;
- navigate the implementation of the ROBIN Toolbox;
- provide their feedback and expertise on the monitoring and evaluation framework to be used after the pilots;
- facilitate access and extend the reach of our consortium to important European stakeholder communities;

- support the wide-spread acceptance and replication of our activities, by acting as project ambassadors who will inform and invite their networks to benefit from them when they are available.

Moreover, the engagement of the AB members in project activities provides ROBIN with access to additional expertise on top of that of the project partners, fueling the development of both technical and strategic results with a strong value as well as consolidating as best as possible the outcomes of the project.

In this context, the process followed to set up the ROBIN AB is described in further detail within the sections that follow.

6.1. Nominations of experts

The setting up of the ROBIN Advisory Board follows an open and transparent process. Experts active in the academia, civil society, private as well as public sector were identified from the professional networks of ROBIN project partners. In fact, each project partner was asked to identify and nominate between 2 and 3 experts. Partners were encouraged to propose candidates from other regions/countries than the pilot regions of the projects, as many stakeholders from the regions are mobilised under WP1 and include experts from key networks such as the SCAR-AKIS SWG, ERRIN etc.

These experts were nominated considering a set of AB member nomination principles, as presented below.

- **The candidates should be in a good working relationship with at least one consortium partner, albeit external to the consortium**
- **The AB shall be composed of experts from different sectors (e.g., (e.g., business community, academia, civil society, governmental bodies) with diverse expertise, gender mix and geographic spread**
- **The experts who will comprise the AB should have very good knowledge and experience in at least one or more of ROBIN fields (i.e., bioeconomy, regional governance and social innovation);**

The nomination phase is finalised and the project partners together identified and nominated over 25 experts across Europe.

The pool of experts nominated by the project partners served as a starting point to select the members of the AB. All partners provided publicly available information (i.e., Name, Organization, Position and Contact Details - email) about the nominated experts.

6.2. Next steps

In the assessment phase, a preliminary screening of the candidates will be performed by WR, ensuring all the forementioned criteria. Then, the partners will be asked to vote up to 2 candidates to join ROBIN's Advisory Board. The rankings of each project partner will be aggregated and an invitee list with potential AB members will be created, taking into account the need for adequate representation in terms of different stakeholder groups, countries, expertise and gender.

Each project partner will invite the selected experts nominated by their organization, providing a Terms of Reference, developed by WR and describing their role, contribution and benefits. The selected experts who will accept the invitation will provide a signed Declaration of Acceptance.

The final composition of the Advisory Board will be reported in Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results – Interim Version.

9. Monitoring, Evaluation, and reporting framework

7.1. Monitoring and evaluation

The monitoring mechanisms are crucial to secure the successful implementation of the D&C strategy and ensure the achievement of the DCP goals: in essence, they measure the impact of the dissemination efforts. Therefore, a monitoring process has been set up at the beginning of the project. This process will support us to identify any potential gaps and problems, the special needs of relevant stakeholders, and good practices that we can adopt. The DCP will be updated - if needed - to include all the modifications and changes due to the monitoring process. In this way, we aim to ensure the effective dissemination of the outcomes to the project's key stakeholders and the general public.

A set of KPIs was selected to evaluate the impact of the DCP activities. Of course, the metric targets and the needs will be adjusted to the project's results and will be included in the updated deliverable (M36). The dissemination manager with the support of the consortium partners will keep track of the quantitative metrics during the reporting periods.

Below is presented the list of KPIs for the dissemination and communication activities of ROBIN:

Table 11. Key Performance Indicators

Assessed element	Metric	Target
<i>Unique visits to the project website</i>	Nr. of visits (total)	> 10,000
<i>Social media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter)</i>	Nr. of followers	> 1,000
<i>Newsletter</i>	Nr. of published Newsletters	6
<i>Project workshops and events</i>	Nr. of workshops	≥ 22
<i>Participation in external events/conferences</i>	Nr. of events	≥ 15
<i>Views of the promotional video</i>	Nr. of views (total)	> 500
<i>Synergies with initiatives & networks</i>	Nr. of joint actions	15
<i>Scientific publications</i>	Nr. of scientific publications	3
<i>Promotional material distributed</i>	Nr. of promotional material distributed	>300
<i>Stakeholders engaged in overall</i>	Nr. of stakeholders engaged	3,000

9.2. Reporting

Keeping track of the dissemination, communication, and engagement activities that were carried out by all partners in the framework of the project is fundamental for its successful implementation. Therefore, reporting and documentation are very important for the DCP. In particular, throughout the duration of the project, all consortium partners should report their dissemination and communication activities on an ad-hoc basis by filling in the template shared by WR (online in the project's repository) each time they perform a dissemination activity. Each semester (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36) WR will consolidate the results and will develop the semestrial technical reporting of WP6.

For keeping track of the activities performed by the consortium partners, a reporting template have been designed and shared (Annex).

Table 12. Annex for Dissemination

Annex	Dissemination Tool	Coverage	When
Annex I	Dissemination reporting template	All dissemination activities carried out by the partners every month.	Ad-hoc basis throughout the project

Dissemination reporting template: This template will record all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The document should be updated by all partners on an ad-hoc basis. Keeping track of the activities will ensure that any problems or gaps will be observed early, and mitigation measures will be put in place in order to be solved. Partners are requested to fill out the form **within 5 days** for any dissemination and communication activity they are involved in. Also, partners are encouraged to inform WR when an event is scheduled and share some brief information (e.g., event, location, dates) as well as take photos & keep the agenda.

Each project partner should immediately contact WR, should any risks be identified concerning communication and dissemination activities, or in case problems arise during the implementation of publicity actions.

10. Timeline and implementation plan

The dissemination and communication activities started at the beginning of the project with the production of the promotional material, will continue with a wide deployment of offline and online dissemination activities, and will be completed with the promotion of the project's final results. On top of that, the project's findings will be promoted even after the end of the project. Figure 17 presents the four different periods during which all our dissemination and communication activities will be implemented.

Figure 17. Summary of ROBIN's timeline

❖ First phase – Early in the project (M1-M6):

During the first phase of the project, the D&C strategy was designed. In the framework of the D&C strategy, several key aspects were identified such as the targeted stakeholder groups that will be reached during the project, as well as the messages that will be used to engage them. In addition, the selection of suitable metrics for monitoring the successful implementation of the strategy took place, and the consortium partners' responsibilities were clearly defined. Furthermore, besides developing the D&C strategy, the first months of the project were dedicated to the production of the dissemination material, as well as the establishment of the dissemination and communication tools. The project's visual identity and logo, the promotional material (leaflet, poster, templates, letterheads), the SMAs, and the project's website was developed in the first 4 months of the project. Finally, the first dissemination of the project to the broader public will take place through contacts with other projects, press releases, the first newsletter, and by participating in external events.

❖ Second phase – During the project (M7 - M25):

Throughout the project, constant interaction between the project partners and the relevant stakeholders will be established. An active community interested in the ROBIN project will be created and maintained through the SMAs. In addition, synergies will be developed with other projects and initiatives relevant to the topics of bioeconomy, bio-based material and industry, sustainability and circular economy, and regional development. Multiple activities are planned to take place within the second phase of the project including dissemination events, workshops, webinars, meetings with the CCRI-CSO, mutual learning workshops, joint events, and dissemination activities with the sister projects. Publications and promotion of the project's results through the website and the bi-annual Newsletter will further maximise the project's impact. Finally, the participation of consortium partners in external events and conferences, as well as their connections to key networks from the sector will be leveraged in order to promote the project to a wider audience.

❖ **Third phase – End of the project (M26 - M36):**

Although the dissemination of the project's vision will continue, this phase of the project will mainly focus on the dissemination of the project's results and outcomes. In particular, toward the end of the lessons learned will permit consortium partners to draft some key recommendations that can support the adoption of sustainability certification schemes. The project's community will be further engaged to ensure its continuation after the project's completion. Furthermore, a final event will be organised aiming to present the project's results, diffuse the knowledge and engage relevant stakeholders in the post-project exploitation of the findings.

❖ **Fourth phase – Beyond the end of the project:**

The ambition of ROBIN'S consortium is to continue promoting the project's vision and results even after the official end of the project ensuring that the project's outcomes will reach as many relevant stakeholders as possible. Relevant publications will further disseminate the project's legacy even after the official completion.

11. Conclusions – Way Forward

The D&C strategy will serve as a guide and will assist the project partners in the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the ROBIN project. Thus, the DCP includes all the communication activities planned during the project's lifetime, the communication channels that will be used to achieve dissemination, and the key messages.

All partners are committed to maximising the potential impact of the outputs of the ROBIN project in terms of its dissemination to all relevant stakeholders, and thus all partners will be actively part of the dissemination activities proposed. A dedicated Work Package (WP5 Dissemination and Exploitation) has been designed to deal with exploitation and dissemination issues and to ensure the use and deep impact of the project results across Europe.

Given the bottom-up, open nature of the project and its activities, the plan will be constantly provided with feedback and thus updated in line with the needs and views of stakeholders. An updated interim version of the DCP will be delivered in M18 based on the experience accumulated during the first 1.5 year of the project. The final version may contain ad-hoc adjustments and updates - if required - to increase and improve the outreach to the targeted stakeholders. This way it is envisaged that the updated version will also enhance the project's vision to the European community at large.

Annexes

Annex I. Dissemination Reporting Template

Title	Deploying circular bioeconomies at regional level with a territorial approach
Acronym	ROBIN
Start	01/03/2022 (M1)
End	31/03/2025 (M36)
Notes:	Please fill out the form within 5 days for any dissemination and communication activity you carry out

The form below has been designed to help you keep track of any kind of communication and dissemination activity you will carry out throughout the project. Dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, press releases, social media posts, website articles, interviews, events (conferences, seminars, workshops, etc.).
 Important: Specify the type of activity as well as the type of the audience(s) addressed using the categories provided in the drop-down menu. These are the categories used in the Participant Portal by the European Commission and it is important that we stick to them.

No. of Action	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity <i>(Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)</i>	Title of conference, workshop, publication, website article, etc.	Size of audience reached per type of stakeholder (in numbers)										Countries addressed <i>(use "global" if the action covers the whole world, use "EU-wide" if the action covers all EU Member States)</i>	Role and description of your organisation's involvement <i>(e.g. facilitator, interviewer, speaker, discussion leader)</i>	Type of project material used <i>(e.g. ROBIN leaflet, ROBIN poster, ROBIN presentation, etc.)</i>	Quantity of project material used <i>(no. of copies distributed per type of project material, use N/A if not applicable)</i>	Other ROBIN partners or external organisations responsible if involved <i>(use N/A if not applicable)</i>	Short description of the action	Other comments <i>(IF RELEVANT)</i>	Significant contacts made if and share data was given <i>(name, position, organisation, tel, e-mail)</i>	
					Scientific Community	Industry	Policy makers	Civil Society	General public	Media	Investors	Customers	Others	Total									
1	Example 10/13/2022	Virtual (zoom)	Participation in activities organized jointly with other Horizon Europe projects	<i>"Implementing circular systemic solutions in cities and regions"</i>	0	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	EU-wide	Speaker	N/A	N/A	N/A	Participation to a joint workshop with representatives of other Horizon Circular Cities projects. Round table for introducing ROBIN and receive information about the progress of other projects.	The participation in the event was successful since the project was introduced to important CS projects, opening new possibilities for synergies.	N/A

Annex II. Collaboration Agreement

a) Template

Collaboration Agreement

between

	<Insert logo of project/ initiative>
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This Collaboration Agreement is signed between:

- 1. ROBIN “Deploying circular Bioeconomies at Regional level with a territorial approach” EU-funded project under grant agreement 101060504**, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by Ioanna Nydrioti (WR, WP leader)
- 2. <Insert name of project/initiative>**, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by <Insert name of the person who will sign this agreement on behalf of the project/ initiative>

The Parties signing this Collaboration Agreement aim to establish a strong liaison between the two projects/initiatives, in terms of bilaterally implementing the following agreed actions. This agreement shall be into force during the agreed period or until termination of the agreement by either Party.

Now, therefore, it is hereby agreed as follows:

WR on behalf of ROBIN agrees to the following:

- Display <Insert project/ initiative> link and logo on the ROBIN website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
 - Distribute <Insert project/ initiative> announcements (e.g. important events) on the ROBIN’s social media platforms.
 - Create announcements on the ROBIN website to promote important <Insert project/ initiative> events.
 - Publish <Insert project/ initiative> (guest) blog posts on the ROBIN’s blog.
 - Invite <Insert project/ initiative> representatives to participate in events organized by ROBIN.
 - Work with <Insert project/ initiative> to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders) together.
-

D5.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan – Initial version

- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of <Insert project/ initiative> on ROBIN social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.
- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of ROBIN and <Insert project/initiative> will be presented.
- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

<Insert name of organisation> **on behalf of** <Insert project/ initiative> **agrees to the following:**

- Display ROBIN link and logo on the <Insert project/ initiative> website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
- Distribute ROBIN announcements (e.g. important events) on the <Insert project/ initiative> social media platforms.
- Create announcements on the <Insert project/ initiative> website to promote important ROBIN events.
- Publish ROBIN (guest) blog posts on the <Insert project/ initiative> blog.
- Invite ROBIN representatives to participate in events organized by <Insert project/ initiative>.
- Work with ROBIN to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders together).
- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of ROBIN on <Insert project/ initiative> social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.
- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of <Insert project/ initiative> and ROBIN will be presented.
- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

Duration:

- Starting from <insert effective date> and ending on the <insert end date>.

Termination:

- Either Party may terminate this Collaboration Agreement immediately by notice upon the other Party.

ROBIN

Per:

Name:

Ioanna Nydrioti

Title:

Project Manager White Research

ROBIN's WP leader DEC

<Insert project/ initiative>

Per:

Name:

Title:

b) Collaboration Agreement with BIOMODEL4REGIONS

Collaboration Agreement

between

This Collaboration Agreement is signed between:

1. ROBIN “Deploying circular Bioeconomies at Regional level with a territorial approach” EU-funded project under grant agreement 101060504, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by Ioanna Nydrioti (WR, WP leader)
2. BIOMODEL4REGIONS, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by Karolina Jurkiewicz (APRE, Task leader of Task 6.4 ‘Clustering with other projects and initiatives’)

The Parties signing this Collaboration Agreement aim to establish a strong liaison between the two projects/initiatives, in terms of bilaterally implementing the following agreed actions. This agreement shall be into force during the agreed period or until termination of the agreement by either Party.

Now, therefore, it is hereby agreed as follows:

WR on behalf of ROBIN agrees to the following:

- Display BIOMODEL4REGIONS link and logo on the ROBIN website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
- Distribute BIOMODEL4REGIONS announcements (e.g. important events) on the ROBIN’s social media platforms.
- Create announcements on the ROBIN website to promote important BIOMODEL4REGIONS events.
- Publish BIOMODEL4REGIONS (guest) blog posts on the ROBIN’s blog.
- Invite BIOMODEL4REGIONS representatives to participate in events organized by ROBIN.
- Work with BIOMODEL4REGIONS to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders) together.
- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of BIOMODEL4REGIONS on ROBIN social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.
- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of ROBIN and BIOMODEL4REGIONS will be presented.

- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

APRE on behalf of BIOMODEL4REGIONS agrees to the following:

- Display ROBIN link and logo on the BIOMODEL4REGIONS website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
- Distribute ROBIN announcements (e.g. important events) on the BIOMODEL4REGIONS social media platforms.
- Create announcements on the BIOMODEL4REGIONS website to promote important ROBIN events.
- Invite ROBIN representatives to participate in events organized by BIOMODEL4REGIONS.
- Work with ROBIN to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders together).
- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of ROBIN on BIOMODEL4REGIONS social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.
- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of BIOMODEL4REGIONS and ROBIN will be presented.
- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

Duration:

- Starting from 1. December.2022 and ending on the 31. August.2025.

Termination:

- Either Party may terminate this Collaboration Agreement immediately by notice upon the other Party.

ROBIN

Per:

Name:
Ioanna Nydrioti

Title:
Project Manager White Research (WR)
ROBIN's WP leader DEC

Signature:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Ioanna Nydrioti', with a period at the end.

BIOMODEL4REGIONS

Per:

Name: Karolina Jurkiewicz

Title: Project Manager, APRE

Signature:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'K. Jurkiewicz', on a light blue background.

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	www.razsk.sk
MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	www.circbio.ie
ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	www.auth.gr
REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	www.pkm.gov.gr
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTTEMBERG GMBH	www.bio-pro.de
SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	www.southernassembly.ie

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